

Effect of Landfilled Fly Ash as a Partial Replacement of Cement on the Compressive Strength of Mortars

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Received : 10 July 2023

Accepted : 30 July 2023

Online : 5 August 2023

Abstract – The aims of this study are to find the optimum percentage of landfilled fly ash that could be used as partial replacement cement and the effect of curing methods on the compressive strength of mortars. The percentages of landfilled fly ash used were 0%, 10%, 20%, 30%, 40%, 50%, 60%, and 70% of cement weight. The cube specimens used were 50 mm x 50 mm x 50 mm. The specimen after curing was tested at the ages of 1, 3, 7, 28, and 56 days. The curing methods applied to the mortars were air drying and water curing, which involved immersing them in a water tank. In the air drying method, the results showed that the compressive strength of the mortar incorporating landfilled fly ash was lower than that of the control mortar in all ages of mortars. At 28 days, only mortar containing 10% landfilled fly ash showed a higher compressive strength than that of similar mortar, but at 56 days, mortar containing up to 30% landfilled fly ash showed a compressive strength close to 45 MPa, which achieves the target of a compressive strength of 40 MPa. Furthermore, 70% of landfilled fly ash mortar at ages of 28 and 56 days achieved compressive strengths of 19 and 20 MPa, respectively. On the other side, using the water curing method, mortars containing up to 30% landfilled fly ash at ages of 28 and 56 days outperformed control mortars. However, mortars containing up to 40% landfilled fly ash had a compressive strength higher than that of the control mortar at 56 days. A 70% landfilled fly ash mortar at ages of 28 and 56 days showed the lowest compressive strengths of 23 and 28 MPa, respectively. Improvements in compressive strength of mortar containing 10%, 20%, and 30% landfilled fly ash in water curing compared to that of control mortar are 13, 17, and 17%, respectively. The 40% partial replacement of cement with landfilled fly ash by either water curing or air curing produced compressive strength mortars above 20 MPa, which is still in the range of normal strength mortar. The effect of the water curing method on the mortars decreased their porosities, and then the mortar became denser, increasing their compressive strength. The different porosities of mortar which partially replacement of cement with up to 40% landfilled fly ash and the control were less than 4%, but the compressive strength of the mortar could increase up to 12% due to water curing.

Keywords: Landfilled Fly Ash, Compressive Strength, Porosity, Mortar, Curing Method

Introduction

Fly ash is a waste of coal burning at the electric generating plant. The plant at North Sumatra produced electric 2x210 MW and burned coal 2,16 million metric tons per year then produced 10% of them as waste such fly ash (Setiawati, 2018) which dumping in open disposal area and creates environmental problem. Prior to 2021, the waste is classified as hazardous and toxic materials (B3) because it contains chemical elements which including silica oxide (SiO₂), alumina oxide (Al₂O₃), iron oxide (Fe₂O₃), and sulfur trioxide (SO₃) (Solikin, Kholishoh, & Setiawan, 2014). Based on estimation from 2014 to 2022 there were 3.5 million tons of fly ash and bottom ash in the ash disposal area of the PLTU. After the decree of PP No. 22 of 2021, fly ash is classified

as a type of non-B3 waste so that fly ash can be used as a building material such as partial replacement for cement in concrete mixtures.

Most researchers reported utilizing fresh fly ash which is coming from silos and its particle size resembles cement and there is also not yet contamination as well. According to ASTM, there are two classes of FAs used in concrete: class F and class C. The burning of bituminous coal produces the class F FA. Class F FA has a low calcium level but a high iron, silica, and alumina content. It is a glassy substance that must be activated with either lime or cement. FA from the burning of lignite and sub-bituminous coal is categorized as class C FA. In comparison to class F FA, it has higher calcium. Class C FA concrete gains strength much more quickly than class F FA concrete (McCarthy & Dyer, 2019). The physical properties of fly ash which are mostly their shape and size have considerable effect on the properties of fly ash-cement system. Further, the suitability of utilizing fly ash as a cement replacement material mostly assessed through its chemical composition (Blissett & Rowson, 2012). Meanwhile, landfilled fly ash is fly ash that dumped in long period of time in open landfilled area. It could be the chemical of landfilled fly ash not much change as Sulc et al. (Šulc et al., 2022) reported that fly ash stockpiles for 50 years showed the performance of chemical properties proved their chemical is still stable. However, they mentioned that a secondary reaction to form CSH could be disturbed due to loss of some important minerals for reacting.

There is limited information on utilizing landfilled fly ash in concrete. It could be due to its particle size is already granulated and they were contaminated by other substances. Itskos et al. (Itskos, Itskos, & Koukouzas, 2010) found that fly ash fraction between 7 and 150 micron produces better pozzolanic properties due to the presence of more intense glass and the phase of weak crystalline. The quantity of fly ash replacement to the cement for a certain application is limited to 15-20% by mass of the total cementitious material (Šulc et al., 2022). Some codes such as British standard (British Standard, 1997) (British Standard, 1977) and India Standard (Indian Standard, 2000) allows a maximum of 35% by mass of fly ash as a cement component can be used. However, Aulia et al. (Aulia, Bahri, Sulaiman, Syaifuddin, & Gusrizal, 2021) reported that granulated fly ash did not need to be ground to resemble the particle size of cement and mentioned that utilizing 20% of granulated fly ash passing sieve #8 improve the compressive strength of mortars better than 10% that that of fly ash grinding through passing sieve # 200. However, there is no information on what optimum percentages of landfilled fly ash affect the strength of mortar. The information on maximum percentages is important for utilizing the landfilled fly ash on concrete in a maximum way to reduce the waste that creates environmental problems as soon as possible.

The curing regime is an essential factor to develop the strength of the concrete. During the hydration process, heat is produced and needs to be brought down by curing for maintaining suitable conditions at the surface of the concrete (Rahimi et al., 2023). The main purpose of curing concrete is to keep the concrete moist during period of developing its strength until water in the pores reduced by hydration process (Gowripalan, Cabrera, Cusens, & Wainwright, 1992).

This study used landfilled fly ash which not resemble the particle size of cement as most researchers reported previously. For these reasons, this paper aims to provide a research findings related to the optimal landfilled fly ash utilization and curing methods on compressive strength of mortar. In addition, this study also shows the relationship between porosities of mortars and their compressive strength

Materials and Methods

The materials for mortars used in this research were landfilled fly ash, cement, fine aggregate, and water. The fly ash used was collected came from landfilled area at the electric generating plant of Pangkalan Susu, North Sumatra, which may be subjected to some minor contamination from soil ground. The original fly ash contains chemical compounds SiO₂ (Silica) 34.81%, CaO (Lime) 25.39%, Al₂O₃ (Alumina) 14.92%, Fe₂O₃ (Iron) 16.49%, and MgO (Magnesia) 4.92% (Rozi, Tarigan, & Perwira, 2020). This type of FA is classified as type C FA based on ASTM C-618 due to the amount of SiO₂, Al₂O₃, and Fe₂O₃ is greater than 50%. The land filled fly ash was sieved passing sieve #8. Figure 1a shows the raw landfilled fly ash and figure 1 b shows landfilled fly ash was

sieved # 8. The cement used is Portland cement type I (OPC) from the Semen Padang brand. This type of cement contains a chemical composition consisting of C3S (Tricalcium Silicate) 55%, C2S (Dicalcium Silicate) 19%, C3A (Tricalcium Alumina) 7%, MgO (Magnesia) 2.8%, and SO₃ (Sulfur Trioxide) 2, 9 % (Ikhwan, Satriawan, & Melwita, 2017). The fine aggregate used comes from the Krueng Tingkeum River, Bireuen. The fine aggregate was first filtered using a sieve #4 (4.75 mm) and then washed to remove dirt. After that, it was rotated and dried in direct to sunlight. The fine aggregate was categorized as in zone II referred to British Standard (British Standard, 1992) and the specific gravity of the fine aggregate was 2.66. Water that used in all mixes was distilled water.

Figure 1. a) The raw landfilled fly ash; b) land filled fly ash after sieving #8

Table 1. Percentages of landfilled fly ash in the mixes of composition mortar and specimen

No.	Mix ID	Percentages of landfilled fly ash (%)	Specimen			Weight material (kg)				
			Air drying	Water curing	Total	Cement	Landfilled fly ash	Fine aggregate	Coarse aggregate	Water
1	MFA-0	0	15	15	30	400	0	714	1071	205
2	MFA-10	10	15	15	30	360	40	714	1071	205
3	MFA-20	20	15	15	30	320	80	714	1071	205
4	MFA-30	30	15	15	30	280	120	714	1071	205
5	MFA-40	40	15	15	30	240	160	714	1071	205
6	MFA-50	50	15	15	30	200	200	714	1071	205
7	MFA-60	60	15	15	30	160	240	714	1071	205
8	MFA-70	70	15	15	30	120	280	714	1071	205

Table 1 shows that the mix proportions of mortar mixes incorporates the percentages of landfilled fly ash as replacement of cement. The control mortar was designed to achieve compressive strength of 40 MPa at 28 days. The mixtures contained constant water/binder (w/b) ratio of 0.51 and total binder content of 400 kg/m³. The ratio of fine aggregate and coarse aggregate adopted in the mix design 4 : 6. However, the aim of this research is to find the strength capacity of mortar so that coarse aggregate was excluded from the mixtures. This study used the partial replacement of cement with landfilled fly ash ranging from 10 % up to-70% with increasing of 10% by weight of cement.

Data collection

The workability of the fresh concretes was measured using a flow table based on BS 1881-105 (British Standard, 1984). The flow table test was conducted directly before fresh mortar was placed into the molds. After placement, the specimens were covered with polyethylene sheet to prevent water evaporation. The mortar moulds were dismantled after 24 h and the specimen were subjected to the curing methods which air draying and water curing. At Air drying curing method, the specimens were put in open shelves at room temperature of the concrete laboratory. For the water curing method, the specimen were emersed in the water tank. The size of cubes specimen was 50 mm x 50 mm x 50 mm. Each mixes was prepared with 15 cubes of air drying and 15 cubes of water curing and the total specimens of 8 mixes are 240 cubes. Furthermore, the specimens were tested after curing for compressive strength at the age of 1, 3, 7, 28, 56 days. The compressive strength testing based on BS 1881-116 (British Standard, 1983b). Table 2. Shows the compressive strength of mortar tested at 1,3,7, 28 and 56 days with different curing methods. Porosity mortar was conducted through measuring water absortion based on BS 1881-122(British Standard, 1983a). Table 3 shows the water absorption (%) mortar at different curring methodods.

Table 2. The Compressive strength of mortar tested at 1,3,7, 28 and 56 days with different curing methods

Mix ID	Curing Method	Compressive Strength (MPa)				
		1 day	3 days	7 days	28 days	56 days
MFA-0	<i>Air Drying</i>	17,44	32,67	42,78	47,70	51,66
	<i>Water</i>		37,61	41,66	51,70	54,71
MFA-10	<i>Air Drying</i>	16,02	33,64	38,84	42,16	46,86
	<i>Water</i>		30,52	35,47	53,20	62,34
MFA-20	<i>Air Drying</i>	14,38	27,56	32,05	38,54	46,16
	<i>Water</i>		27,39	41,06	59,26	64,02
MFA-30	<i>Air Drying</i>	14,53	25,39	30,20	37,10	46,86
	<i>Water</i>		26,07	37,11	54,25	63,49
MFA-40	<i>Air Drying</i>	7,70	16,19	25,00	33,96	41,09
	<i>Water</i>		18,88	27,68	46,88	54,32
MFA-50	<i>Air Drying</i>	5,68	11,11	20,23	27,70	34,29
	<i>Water</i>		11,78	18,98	38,16	41,73
MFA-60	<i>Air Drying</i>	3,46	8,99	13,88	21,91	23,39
	<i>Water</i>		8,06	15,14	32,72	32,86
MFA-70	<i>Air Drying</i>	2,11	6,14	11,57	19,45	20,96
	<i>Water</i>		5,77	11,40	23,46	28,73

Table 3. Water absorption (%) mortar at different curing methods

Mix ID	Curing Method	Water absorption (%)				
		1 day	3 days	7 days	28 days	56 days
MFA-0	<i>Air Drying</i>	12,51	11,34	10,88	10,70	11,08
	<i>Water</i>		11,89	11,57	11,43	10,62
MFA-10	<i>Air Drying</i>	12,47	11,61	11,34	10,99	11,08
	<i>Water</i>		11,95	11,83	11,67	10,51
MFA-20	<i>Air Drying</i>	12,68	11,64	11,15	10,92	11,16
	<i>Water</i>		12,11	11,61	11,33	10,37
MFA-30	<i>Air Drying</i>	11,75	11,21	11,08	10,49	11,03
	<i>Water</i>		11,69	11,62	11,49	10,45
MFA-40	<i>Air Drying</i>	13,05	12,61	11,82	11,10	11,80
	<i>Water</i>		12,83	12,53	11,91	10,72
MFA-50	<i>Air Drying</i>	13,59	12,54	12,32	11,93	12,24
	<i>Water</i>		13,27	12,97	12,34	11,85
MFA-60	<i>Air Drying</i>	13,84	12,84	12,72	12,27	13,22
	<i>Water</i>		13,69	13,51	13,28	12,21
MFA-70	<i>Air Drying</i>	14,27	13,27	12,85	12,67	13,42
	<i>Water</i>		13,88	13,74	13,43	12,51

Results

At this stage the percentage of landfilled fly ash substitution is used, namely 0%, 10%, 20%, 30%, 40%, 50%, 60%, and 70% of the cement weight. Figure 2. shows the increasing compressive strength of fly ash mortar by air drying curing method. It shows that all the compressive strength of landfilled fly ash mortar experienced lower than that of control mortar at ages up to 56 days. Only mortar contained 10% landfilled fly ash shows the compressive strength better than that of other similar mortar and this type mortar could achieve the target compressive strength as 40 MPa at ages of 28 days. However, the mortar contained landfilled fly ash up to 30% could achieve the target strength 40 MPa above 56 days. The mortar contained 70% landfilled fly ash only can achieve its strength 20 MPa above ages of 56 days.

At the age of 28 days, the compressive strength of MFA-30 increased by 16.22% from the age of 7 days. In air drying conditions (room temperature) 20°C to 35°C fly ash slows down cement hydration of cement in mortar at the beginning ages (Narmluk & Nawa, 2011). In the air-drying method, the control mortar condition achieved the highest compressive strength at the age of 56 days. The slow effect of C2S on MFA-0 affecting the strength of cement that occurs at a longer age. So that the production of CSH from C2S and H₂O is more optimal at the age of the mortar reaching 56 days (Widojoko, 2010). Pozzolan such as rice husk and fly ash can make mortar denser because it reacts with CaOH from hydrated cement to produce other CSH but this condition reacts slowly (Bahri, Mahmud, Shafiqh, & Majuar, 2019).

Figure 3. shows the developing compressive strength of landfilled fly ash mortar by water curing method. It shows that some the compressive strength of mortar contained landfilled fly ash up to 40% experienced higher than that of control mortar at ages up to 56 days. The mortar contained landfilled fly ash 50 up to 70% shows the compressive strength lower than that of the control mortar. The mortar contained land filled fly ash up to 30 % could achieve the target compressive strength as 40 MPa at ages of 28 days. However, the mortar contained landfilled fly ash up to 30% could achieve the target strength 40 MPa above 56 days. The mortar contained 70% landfilled fly ash only can achieve its strength 28 MPa above ages of 56 days.

Figure 2. Development of Compressive Strength of Mortar on Air Drying Curing method

Figure 3. Development of Compressive Strength of Mortar on Water Curing method

The mortar contained landfilled flyash up to 30% develops their strength until the age of 56 days. The developed strength was due to a large amount of calcium hydroxide (CH) available and react with SiO₂ from pozzolan material such as landfilled fly ash fly ash and then produce CSH and create mortar denser and increase

(Bahri, Mahmud, & Shafiqh, 2018). In water curing method, the substitution of 20% fly ash by weight of cement and in the highest compressive strength. According to Termkhajornkit et al. (Termkhajornkit, Nawa, & Kurumisawa, 2006) hydration of fly ash mortar is better in water curing method. When the water-to-cement ratio is quite low, the hydration of the cement along with a small amount of fly ash is sufficient to provide compressive strength at the initial age of the mortar. The content of SiO_2 , Al_2O_3 , and Fe_2O_3 affects the reaction of pozzolan (Cho, Ung, & Choi, 2019). The pozzolanic reaction in fly ash decreased with the fly ash substitution in mortar. This is due to the incomplete pozzolanic reaction. The use of higher volume of fly ash causes excess SiO_2 which cannot be completely melted with $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$ so the mortar process could not complete its reaction (Saha, 2018).

Figure 4. Comparison of the Compressive Strength of Mortar in Air Drying and Water Curing Methods

Figure 4 shows a comparison of the developing compressive strength of mortars incorporating landfilled fly ash up to 40% in the air-drying and water-curing methods. At the initial age up to age of 7 days, the MFA-0 of air drying and water curing increased significantly. This situation was reversed at age of 56 days mortar of MFA-20, MFA-30, and MF40 in water curing methos increased significantly to reach 62 MPa at 56 days of age. Pozzolanic reaction in water-curing fly ash mortar may still require H_2O to react with SiO_2 to produce more CSH so that the strength is more than fly ash air-drying methodes. However, this process occurs more slowly (Lamine Zeggar, Azline, & Azizi Safiee, 2019). The reduction in strength with the inclusion of fly ash at an early age of mortar is due to the slow pozzolanic reaction of the low calcium ash, especially during an early age with only some part of the fly ash participating in the reaction (Rashad, 2015). The results showed that the water-curing mortar produced a better compressive strength than the air-drying methodes. The pozzolanic reaction is better carried out in the air, with sufficient humidity and a long time (Srinath, Ramesh, Patnaikuni, Vani, & Potharaju, 2021). Utilizing landfill fly ash between 50 up to 70% reduced compressive strength significantly. However, utilizing high volume fly ash concrete (HVFC) can reduce the quantity of cement used, lowering greenhouse gas emissions while successfully recycling fly ash as an industrial byproduct (Sengul, Tasdemir, Yuceer, Erbaydar, & Tasdemir, 2002).

Air drying of the mortar and water preservation that have been carried out after the strength test is then obtained the proportion of air absorption to determine the effect of the preservation conditions on the porosity of the mortar.

Figures 5. Porosities development of Mortars in Air Drying Curing Methods

Figures 5 shows reducing porosities of landfilled fly ash and control mortar in air drying curing methods. It is clearly shown that most mortars contained landfilled fly ash have higher porosities than that of control mortar up to ages of 56 days. above 100% mean that their porosity is higher than control mortar. Only mortar MFA-30 at age of 56 days shows its relative porosity is 98% which is lower than that of control mortar. The decrease in porosity of air-drying fly ash mortar with increasing mortar age. The pore content in the mortar affects the strength of the mortar. The increase landfilled fly ash in mortars causes the increasing proportion of porosity of mortar in the air drying curing methods and decreases the strength of mortars.

Figures 6. Relative Porosities of Mortars compared to control mortar in Water Curing Methods

Figure 6 shows a decreasing relative porosity of the landfilled fly ash mortar in water-curing methods. The addition of fly ash up to 40% decreased pore content in mortar. The lowest porosity was obtained from MFA-20 at the age of 56 days. The use of fly ash is able to change the pores larger than that in control mortar to be smaller due to pozzolanic reaction along with the cement hydration process. According to Rashad (Rashad, 2015) the use of fly ash decrease the porosity and water absorption due to the pozzolnic reaction in the mixture. Cement hydration is able to fill the initial volume occupied by air, thereby reducing the total porosity of the system.

Figures 7. Comparison Relative Porosities of Mortars between Air curing and Water Curing Methods

Figure 7 shows a comparison of the relative porosities of mortar in the air-drying and water-curing methods. At the initial age up to age of 7 days, the MFA-0 of air drying and water curing increased significantly. This situation was reversed at age of 56 days mortar of MFA-20, MFA-30, and MF40 in water curing methos increased significantly to reach 62 MPa at 56 days of age. Pozzolanic reaction in water-curing fly ash mortar may still require H₂O to react with SiO₂ to produce more CSH so that the strength is more than fly ash air-drying methodes.

Conclusion

Based on the research that has been done, it can be ascertained that the replacement of 20% landfilled fly ash in the mortar produces a compressive strength 12% higher than that of the control mortar. The compressive strength of mortars is related to their porosities. The higher the compressive strength of mortars, the lower their porosities. Increasing the proportion of landfilled fly ash above 40% increases the pore space in the mortar. The use of 20% landfilled fly ash reduced the porosity by more than that of the control mortar. In addition, the curing of mortars affects the strength of the mortar. Mortar curing in water has a higher compressive strength than mortar in air-drying curing. The compressive strength of mortar in water curing could achieve up to 17% higher than that of control mortar. Mortar curing in water reduces porosities in mortar, thereby increasing its compressive strength.

Acknowledgment

The authors would like to thank the Research and Society Service Center of Lhokseumawe State Polytechnic for awarding the grant to carry out research related to landfilled fly ash. The authors also acknowledge the students, Siti Aja Aulia, Fenny Nadilla Putri, Mukhtaruddin, Muhammad Aqro Reza, and Muhammad Nizar Ali, for laboratory tests. The help of PLTU Pangkalan Susu in supplying landfilled fly ash is highly appreciated.

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